

**FOOD POISONING (TOXICOINFECTIONS). ETIOLOGY. EPIDEMIOLOGY.
PATHOGENESIS AND PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES. CLINICAL SIGNS
AND CLASSIFICATION. DIAGNOSIS. TREATMENT. PREVENTION**

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Abstract. This article describes in detail about food poisoning, its etymology, causes and practical treatment in medicine.

Key words: food poisoning, clinical cases, botulism, microbes, pancreas, treatment, etc.

In summer and autumn, every household prepares pickles and preserves from fruits and vegetables. And in winter, these products become the beauty of our table and we love to eat them with our family. But not everyone knows that there is a possibility of food poisoning during the consumption of these products. There are such diseases that the symptoms of the disease do not attract much attention, but their consequences can even lead to death. Botulism is an example of this. After all, this disease is found among the residents of our district, even if it is rare. Botulism is a disease caused by eating contaminated food products (such as canned fruits and vegetables, smoked fish, and sausages) as a result of botulism bacilli producing a strong toxin when exposed to a favorable environment. Under normal conditions, botulism microbes are in the spore state, and they are considered absolutely safe. Botulism microbes in the form of thousands of spores can be observed when soil samples taken from the environment are viewed under a microscope.

A microbe that falls into an airless environment (canning can, between the skin of smoked fish) immediately switches from the spore state to the vegetative state and begins to produce a strong poison (endotoxin). As a result, the lid of the can of canned goods swells (bombage), the inside of the lid becomes rusty. But in most cases, it is not possible to distinguish a contaminated product with the naked eye. The disease can begin 2-4 hours after eating the contaminated product, sometimes 10-12 hours, and in some cases after 1-2 days. It depends, first of all, on the

immune status of the body, and then on the amount of the product consumed. The main symptoms of the disease are nausea, vomiting, heaviness in the stomach, weakness, difficulty swallowing, blurred vision, and double vision. In medicine, this condition is called "diplopia". If the patient is not treated in time, i.e., if the specific serum is not given depending on the type of the disease, the patient may die due to heart and respiratory failure.

Food poisoning is caused by eating food contaminated by toxins or pathogens (such as bacteria). Common symptoms include stomach pain, diarrhea, and vomiting. Food poisoning usually clears up on its own within a few days. But in more severe cases, patients should be treated in a hospital. Symptoms of food poisoning (including food poisoning) can vary slightly depending on the cause. Classic characters that almost always appear:

- nausea
- Vomiting
- diarrhea
- Stomach cramps

There are many other pathogens that can cause foodborne illness. Some examples and typical symptoms of infection are: Escherichia coli: E. coli bacteria is found mainly in raw cattle and raw milk. It can also be spread from person to person. E. coli infection causes diarrhea that is initially watery and then bloody. Staphylococci: These bacteria can spread from hands to food when handled improperly in the kitchen, causing food poisoning (heating food does not kill germs). Symptoms are low temperature and poor blood circulation. Yersinia: Yersinia bacteria are usually transmitted by contact with infected animals or by eating contaminated animal feed. Common symptoms of the disease are headache, chills and fever. Campylobacter: Campylobacter bacterium is mainly found in undercooked poultry and raw egg products. It can be killed by cooking. Symptoms of Campylobacter food poisoning include high fever, headache, fatigue, and watery diarrhea. Shigella: These germs are common in warm places where hygiene is poor, where garbage or sewage contaminates food or drinking water. Food poisoning caused by Shigella causes abdominal pain, painful bowel movements, and diarrhea. Complications: In some cases, food poisoning can lead to dehydration, hemolytic uremic syndrome, or other complications.

Dehydration is the most common complication of food poisoning. When food poisoning causes you to vomit or have diarrhea, your body loses fluids and electrolytes. If you don't replace these fluids and electrolytes, you can become dehydrated. If you're dehydrated, your body doesn't have enough fluids and electrolytes to function properly. Dehydration is especially

dangerous for children, adults and people with weakened immune systems. If you become dehydrated, seek medical attention immediately to prevent serious health problems. Without treatment, dehydration can lead to problems such as organ damage, coma, or even death. Hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) is a kidney disease that occurs when red blood cells are destroyed and block the kidney's filtration system. If your kidneys stop working, you have acute kidney injury - a sudden and temporary loss of kidney function. The most common cause of hemolytic uremic syndrome is infection with a strain of Escherichia coli (E. coli) bacteria called E. coli, but other bacteria and viruses can also cause the condition. (HUS) often occurs in children under 5 years of age.

Food poisoning is an acute illness usually accompanied by indigestion. The reason for this is often the entry of various microorganisms into the body together with food. Most cases of food poisoning are caused by the rapid growth of Staphylococcus aureus and Escherichia coli in products. Poisoning is often caused by consumption of low-quality products that have expired, stored in improper conditions, or manufactured in violation of sanitary standards. Food poisoning is also observed when eating poisonous mushrooms and plants. At the first signs of food poisoning, it is necessary to wash the patient's stomach to empty it. For washing, a weak (pale pink) solution of potassium permanganate (mangansovka) passed through a paper filter or four layers of gauze can be used. In addition, a solution of baking soda (1 teaspoon for 1 liter of boiled water) or table salt (2 tablespoons without "stone" for 5 liters of water) is also suitable. The washing solution should be prepared in advance in the amount of 8-10 liters. It must be warm (at a temperature of 35-37 °C) so as not to cause hypothermia of the body, as well as not to slow down intestinal peristalsis. At the first reception, drink 2-3 to 5-6 glasses of liquid, then stimulate the root of the tongue with two fingers and induce vomiting. The washing process is repeated until there is only clean water in the sludge. After washing the stomach, it is recommended to take enterosorbents with boiled water four times every 15 minutes. It is necessary to leave the patient in peace, if he is suffocating, he should be kept warm. It is better to refrain from eating on the first day, and on the second day you can add broth, rice and vegetable soups and gradually expand the menu. Until complete recovery, it is necessary to avoid eating marinated, spicy, salty and smoked products that irritate the gastric mucosa. The patient is recommended to drink boiled water, sweet tea that is not bitter, fruit juices, jelly. Carbonated drinks are prohibited.

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